

THE EFFECT OF PERPENDICULARITY ERROR ON STRESS CONCENTRATION FOR CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTIC

Xueshu Liu¹, Jian Wang², Hang Gao², Yongjie Bao², Lei Chen³, Rupeng Li³, Renke Kang²

¹ School of Automotive Engineering, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, P.R. China.

E-mail: liuxs@dlut.edu.cn

² School of Mechanical Engineering, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian 116024, P.R. China.

³ Shanghai Aircraft Manufacturing Co. Ltd., Shanghai 200120, P.R. China.

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ABSTRACT

Defects appeared in the machining process of bolt-hole in carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) weaken the strength of bolted joint and may cause unexpected disasters. The effects of perpendicularity error of bolt-hole on stress distribution in CFRP and stress concentration were investigated in the present work. A finite element model was developed and serial numerical investigations were carried out to reveal the stress distribution caused by bolt load in CFRP. In addition, the perpendicularity error of bolt-hole had been proved to greatly affect not only the stress distribution but also the stress concentration factor around the bolt-hole. It was found that when perpendicularity error of bolt-hole increases up to 4° the stress in the area around the bolt-hole may increase more than 20 times.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) has been widely used in aerospace due to its high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratio. Although CFRP is manufactured near-net shape, which has significantly decreased the number of joints for assembly and increased the structure safety as well, mechanical joints like bolted joints are still indispensable for large and complex structure fabrication due to their high reliability, accessibility for maintenance tasks and cost-saving [1]. However, it was reported that 60-85% of failures occurred at joints and they have become the weakest parts of CFRP structures.

Bolted joints should be carefully designed not only for the purpose of high responsibility applications on CFRP but also due to the fact that bolted joints for CFRP are significantly more complicated than their metallic counterparts because of the brittle nature of CFRP and the additional failure modes not present in metal structures. That the enhanced stress concentration factor (SCF) at the surrounding of the bolt-hole and the weakness of the CFRP under out-of-plane loads makes the designing and assembly process more critical in the case of mechanical joints for CFRP. Hence, an understanding of the strength of bolted joint is essential to the design of CFRP structures. To this end, numerous efforts have been made to determine the effect of bolting parameters on the strength of bolted joint. The reported works include geometric factors [2-11], material properties [12-15], coefficients of friction [16-18], bolt shape [19,20], clearance [18,21-31], and torque [6,14,31-36]. In addition, defects occurred during CFRP manufacturing and machining weaken the strength of bolted joint too. Damaged free and precise bolt-holes should be machined in CFRP components to ensure high joint strength and precision. Unfortunately, it is almost impossible to machine the bolt-hole without any defect due to many limitations. Delamination has attracted researchers' attentions for decades since it directly leads to failures occurred at joints [37-41]. On the other hand, geometrical defects including error of perpendicularity of bolt-hole attract fewer eyeballs though they affect the stress distribution surrounding the bolt-hole and enhance SCF as well. To the authors' best knowledge, only few researchers so far focus on the effect of geometrical accuracy on strength of joint [42].

The main objectives of the present work are to perform stress analysis around bolt-hole in CFRP plates with and without taking perpendicularity error into consideration and to show the effect of

perpendicularity error of bolt-hole on the strength of bolted joint.

2 NUMERICAL MODEL

2.1 Problem statement

The configuration of the composite structure contains two bolt-holes Φ in diameter and r in radius (Fig.1). One is intentionally designed with perpendicularity error θ (EH for short) and the other is not (NH for short). That is $\theta_{EH} \neq 0$ and $\theta_{NH} = 0$. Figure 1 also shows the reference coordinate system $x-y-z$ and defines the plate width $2W$, length L , thickness t , distance d between the centric axes of the two bolt-holes and distance e from the center of EH to edge. Note that the center of EH indicates the intersection point between the axis of EH and the top surface S of the structure.

Figure 1: Configuration of the single-lap two bolt-holes composite structure

As shown in Fig.2, the perpendicularity error θ indicates the acute angle between the real axis $L3$ and the designed axis $L4$ of EH in the plane P through $L3$ and $L4$. In addition, the angle of inclination α is defined as the angle starting from $L1$ to $L2$ in anticlockwise direction in S , where $L2 = P \cap S$. By this way, the posture of EH can be clearly specified by θ and α in three directional space.

Figure 2: The specification of EH

Considering the test standard of American Society for Testing and Materials, ASTM D5961/D5961M-13, the symmetry of the composite structure and the possible tolerance used in practice, the geometrical conditions and bolt-hole with different gestures are listed in Table 1, where the length is given in (mm) and angle is given in ($^{\circ}$).

L	w	t	d	e	Φ	θ	α
80	20	3	40	20	6	0 1.0 2.0 3.0	0 45 90

Table 1: Parameters used in this literature

2.2 Material properties

An orthotropic material system of 16 plies of carbon-epoxy HTA 7/6376 with stacking sequence $[45/-45/0/90]_{2s}$ is considered for plates for the analysis. The mechanical properties of a single lamina of unidirectional HTA 7/6376 in the principal directions are $E_1 = 145$ GPa, $E_2 = 10.3$ GPa, $E_3 = 11.1$ GPa, $G_{12} = 5.3$ GPa, $G_{13} = 5.27$ GPa, $G_{23} = 3.95$ GPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.3$, $\nu_{13} = 0.3$, $\nu_{23} = 0.5$ [18]. The bolt joint 6 mm in nominal diameter is made of Ti6Al4V and its elastic module is $E = 110$ GPa and Poisson's ratio is 0.21.

2.3 Contact and boundary conditions

Note that the bolt and washer were considered as a titanium single solid to decrease the contact surfaces and shorten the processing time as well. Therefore, there were four solids in finite element model: two CFRP plates, the nut and the bolt-washer solid as shown in Fig.3.

Figure 3: Boundary conditions and contact interactions

The contact interactions were modeled using surface-based contact considering a linear penalty method. There are totally five contact pairs between the four solids in the whole model. Two of them are located between the fasteners shanks and holes (two contact pairs), two of them are between fastener heads/nuts and the outer surfaces of the two plates (two contact pairs), and one of them is between the faying surface of two plates (one contact pair).

Finite sliding formulation was adopted to model all the contact relationships. The level of bolt-hole clearance in the models is zero to represent a near-fit specimen. In addition, model friction coefficients were ignored due to the static simulation fact.

The bolt load was implemented in the finite element model by introducing a pre-tension condition. This pre-tensioning was simulated by adding a 'cutting surface' in the bolt and subjecting it to a normal load. The relation between the applied torque T and the bolt load F can be calculated as [18]:

$$F = \frac{T}{k \phi} \quad (1)$$

where ϕ is the bolt diameter, k is the torque coefficient usually taken as 0.2.

For the sake of simplicity, the NH was fixed and a bolt pre-load was applied in an initial step and replicated the torque condition applied to the bolt.

2.4 Mesh

The aim of this study is to analyze the stress distribution around the bolt-hole and the effect of perpendicularity error of bolt-hole on stress concentration. To this end, polar coordinate system was adopted and shown in Fig.4. The pole O locates the center of EH and the polar axis ξ shares the same direction with x as shown in Fig.1. The red dots represent some of sampling points $\{p\}$ used to evaluate the influence of perpendicularity error of bolt-hole on stress concentration and each of them can be clearly specified by polar angle β and radius ξ , namely $p(\beta, \xi)$, where $\beta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 135^\circ, 180^\circ$ and $\xi = r, 2r, 3r$ are used after taking the symmetry of the plate and the possible region affected by bolt load into consideration [43-45]. Moreover, $p(\beta, \xi, \pi_i)$ is used to signify a sampling point in three dimensional space, where π_i indicates the layer i of the plate. For a plate its layers are numbered in Z direction (Fig.1), which starts from 1 and ends with 16, that is $i = 1, 2, \dots, 16$.

Figure 4: Sampling points for mesh refinement

A mesh refinement process was carried out to assure that results were not dependent on the element size. Successive space discretizations were compared varying the element size from 0.5 mm to 2 mm with a 0.5 mm span in the surrounding of the hole. Stresses at sampling points $p(\beta, \xi, \pi_{10})$ are shown in Fig.5 and the characteristic element size in the final mesh in layer was 0.5 mm. In addition, the effect of the number of elements through thickness on the results was also studied and 16-element through the thickness was adopted in the present work on the foundation of results shown in Fig.6. Although these characteristic element sizes were enough to provide accurate results without an expensive computational cost, the mesh density used was further increased to 0.1 mm at locations where high stress gradients were anticipated (Fig.7).

Figure 5: Stresses at sampling points in the 10th layer vary according to mesh size

Figure 6: Stresses at sampling points vary according to the number of elements through thickness

Figure 7: Refined mesh used in the present work. Meshes in the region of high stress gradients are further refined

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Stress distribution in anisotropic material

Stress caused by bolted joint in isotropic material had been well studied and its distribution envelope is of conical and spherical (Fig.8 (a)) [46,44]. But for CFRP, the stress distribution envelope shows different from section view to section view. For the latitudinal section which was obtained by cutting the plate with a plane parallel to YZ plane, the stress distribution through thickness is similar to that of isotropic material (Fig.8 (b)). Nevertheless, for the longitudinal section obtained by cutting the plate with a plane parallel to XY plane, the stress distribution envelope is inverted conical shape for

one plate (Fig.8 (c)). This should be caused by the anisotropic properties of CFRP.

(a) Stress distribution envelope

(b) Transverse section, $\theta = 0^\circ$

(c) Longitudinal section, $\theta = 0^\circ$

Figure 8: Stress distribution envelopes show different from that of isotropic material

Perpendicularity error of bolt-hole has great effect on stress distribution in CFRP. When the hole is machined perfectly, that is $\theta = 0^\circ$, the stress caused by bolt load shows well-balanced in the region covered by washer (Fig.9 (a)). However, when θ exists, the stress becomes highly concentrated (Fig.9 (b)). The stress distribution in material also changes significantly (Fig.9(c) and Fig.9 (d)).

(a) $\theta = 0^\circ$

(b) $\alpha = 180^\circ, \theta = 3^\circ$

(c) Longitudinal section, $\alpha = 180^\circ, \theta = 3^\circ$

(d) Transverse section, $\alpha = 180^\circ, \theta = 3^\circ$

Figure 9: Perpendicularity error of bolt-hole affects stress distribution.

3.2 Stress increasing caused by θ

In this section, stress caused by perpendicularity error of bolt-hole was analyzed. To illustrate the stress gradient in the region around the bolt-hole, more sampling points were selected as shown in

Fig.7 in red dots in $\beta = 0^\circ$. The changes of stresses at these sampling point over θ are shown in Fig.10 and Fig.11, whose bolt-hole's inclination angles are $\alpha = 180^\circ$ and $\alpha = 225^\circ$ respectively.

It can be clearly seen from Fig.10 that the stresses at sampling points increase with the increasing of θ . Sampling points in $\beta = 0^\circ$ suffer from the maximum stresses. This is due to the fact that the bolt load drives the bolt to move against its inclination direction, namely in the direction of $\beta = 0^\circ$.

Figure 10: Perpendicularity error of bolt-hole affects stress distribution. Stresses at sampling points increase with the increasing of θ .

Even the inclination direction of bolt-hole a changes the stresses at sampling points increase with the increasing of θ (Fig.11). But the maximum stress does not appear in the opposite direction of a as previous one does. The sampling points in the direction of $\beta = 0^\circ$ still bear the maximum stresses but a

little lower compared with that shown in Fig.10(a). Sampling points in the direction of $\beta= 0^\circ$ and $\beta= 90^\circ$ nearly share the same increasing of stress. It is believed that this is caused by lay-up sequence of CFRP plate.

Figure 11: The anisotropic property of CFRP also affects the stress distribution.

3.3 Stress concentration caused by θ

The SCF caused by θ can be computed by following equation

$$\text{SCF}_\theta = \max\left\{\frac{\sigma_{(p,\theta)}}{\sigma_{(p,0)}}\right\} \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_{(p,\theta)}$ indicates the stress at sampling point p around a bolt-hole with perpendicularity error θ .

The effect of θ on SCF is shown in Table 2. Generally speaking, the results agree that with the increasing of θ stress in the region around the bolt-hole increases. When θ increases up to 4° , the stress

may increase more than 20 times no matter which direction the bolt-hole inclines.

$\alpha/^\circ$	$\beta/^\circ$	SCF $_{\theta}$			
		$\theta=1^\circ$	$\theta=2^\circ$	$\theta=3^\circ$	$\theta=4^\circ$
180	0	4.1	9.9	14.4	19.4
	45	4.7	11.1	17.1	21.8
	90	3.2	4.5	7.3	9.4
	135	1.8	11.2	7.2	10.4
	180	2.8	5.5	5.3	11.8
225	0	4.1	6.3	9.8	13.4
	45	2.8	7.1	10.4	13.3
	90	7.1	10.9	16.0	20.6
	135	2.6	3.8	6.3	8.1
	180	5.9	3.6	4.9	5.4

Table 2: Stress concentration factor caused by θ

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a three-dimensional finite element method was proposed and utilized to study the effects of perpendicularity error of bolt-hole on stress distribution and concentration of a composite single-lap two-bolt joint. Through the analysis of the simulation results, it can be concluded that:

- Stress distribution in anisotropic material shows different from that of isotropic material. The stress distribution envelope in anisotropic material varies from section to section, which is caused by the anisotropic property of the material.
- With the increasing of perpendicularity error of bolt-hole, stress in the region around the bolt-hole increases. Usually the region in the opposite direction against the bolt-hole inclination direction suffers from the most increasing of stress. This may vary if lay-up sequence of CFRP changes.
- Perpendicularity error of bolt-hole has great effect on not only the stress distribution but also the magnitude of stress in the region surrounding the bolt-hole. It was found that when it grew up to 4° the stress increased more than 20 times.

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